

Juju/MAAS for free?

As viewed from the sideline

Background

Current system

- Newton release via Openstack ansible (OSA)
- Old outdated HW on controlplane and hypervisors and Ceph system

New system

- Rocky release via Openstack ansible (OSA)
- New hardware on controlplane (and hypervisors and a new Ceph system)

Project approach

- Design document and project plan (review and approval)
- Building and transferring knowledge, one new and one experienced

First impressions of OSA

- Modular approach, base operating system + packages pre reqs
- Requires networking planned and preconfigured
- Perceived as a moving target in terms of running playbooks
- There is a large community
- Primary interacts via IRC

First impressions of Juju/MAAS

- Holistic approach to installing Openstack
- Seems to hide the complexity in for instance neutron networking at a first glance (pun intended)
- Create your own charms (yay, or ..)
- There is a community (around charms)
- Where to interact .. Canonical?

The canonical Openstack offer

- Two week delivery
- \$75k including operational education for your staff
- \$150k for a HPC optimisation / GPU support
- No downtime upgrades

How did it look?

Conclusions

- Fail fast, fail often?
- Having limited staff requires heavy immersion i.e limited split time
- Will require heavy lifting by yourselves (do not underestimate this)
- Is \$75,000 really that much, or is it \$150,000 (inc HPC optimisation)
- Canonical is not really competing with Openstack